

Weijie Zhang^{1,a}, Yiding Li^{1,b}, Ying Yan^{1,c}, Shibo Yan^{1,d}, and Xi Zou^{2,e}

¹ School of Aeronautic Science and Engineering, Beihang University, No. 37 Xueyuan Road, Haidian District, Beijing, China, 100191

² Faculty of Science and Engineering, Swansea University, Swansea, Wales, UK

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Background & Aims

- Laminated structures used in aviation industry
 - complex structural
 - out-plane loading conditions
- Analysis of strength and progressive damage
 - nonlinear behavior after damage initiation
 - High time cost

- A surrogate model for laminated stiffened panels

Methods

$$\frac{\partial N}{\partial E} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial E_1} & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial E_2} & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial E_3} & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial E_4} & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial E_5} & \frac{\partial N_1}{\partial E_6} \\ \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial E_1} & \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial E_2} & \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial E_3} & \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial E_4} & \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial E_5} & \frac{\partial N_2}{\partial E_6} \\ \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial E_1} & \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial E_2} & \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial E_3} & \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial E_4} & \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial E_5} & \frac{\partial N_3}{\partial E_6} \\ \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial E_1} & \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial E_2} & \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial E_3} & \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial E_4} & \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial E_5} & \frac{\partial N_4}{\partial E_6} \\ \frac{\partial N_5}{\partial E_1} & \frac{\partial N_5}{\partial E_2} & \frac{\partial N_5}{\partial E_3} & \frac{\partial N_5}{\partial E_4} & \frac{\partial N_5}{\partial E_5} & \frac{\partial N_5}{\partial E_6} \\ \frac{\partial N_6}{\partial E_1} & \frac{\partial N_6}{\partial E_2} & \frac{\partial N_6}{\partial E_3} & \frac{\partial N_6}{\partial E_4} & \frac{\partial N_6}{\partial E_5} & \frac{\partial N_6}{\partial E_6} \end{bmatrix}$$

FE model established by CLT

Training

calculate DDNDDE in Fortran

ABAQUS (ugens) for FE analysis

Results & Conclusion

- After 14 iterations, the fitting effect for a specific load condition has been significantly improved

- The results of the individual loading of the six variables indicate that the ANN can proficiently serve as a proxy for the strain-stress relationship.

- The computational principle behind the generalized stress and the Jacobian matrix (DDNDDE in ugens).

- The load-displacement curve of tensile in laminated plates, and the strain nephogram in the x-direction

- The strain nephogram of laminated stiffened panels under out-plane load

- The ANN surrogate model, established based on CLT, can effectively reflect the progressive damage process of laminates, and accurately depict the generalized stress-strain relationship experienced by reinforced laminates under out-of-plane loads and other conditions.
- Due to the reduction in the number of elements and conditional and assignment statements, there is also a certain improvement in computational efficiency